

Predictive Factors for Health Service Utilization in Rural Ghana: A Community-Based Analytical Study

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ABSTRACT: Achieving universal healthcare coverage in rural Ghana continues to be challenging despite considerable investments in the health system. This study predicted factors influencing health service utilization among residents in rural Ghana, to guide evidence-based strategies aimed at enhancing universal coverage. A community-based analytical study was conducted involving 1,738 adults. Participants were selected using multistage sampling method and a structured questionnaire based on the Andersen Behavioral Model was adopted. Chi-square tests, binary logistic regression, and multiple linear regression analyses were conducted using Stata 12.0, with statistical significance set at $p < 0.05$. Results indicated that age, educational level, marital status, and monthly income were significant predictors of health service utilization. Also, rural resident with tertiary education were 1.99 times more likely to utilize health services than those with no formal education. Rural dwellers earning above GH¢2,000 monthly were 3.21 times more likely to utilize services than those earning below GH¢500. Unmarried individuals were 0.09 times less likely to utilize healthcare services compared to married ones. Health facility factors; distance, cost of treatment, perceived quality of care, and waiting time, explained 69.5% of the variation in health service utilization, where cost of treatment had the strongest influence. Health provider factors, including worker's attitude, job knowledge, work experience, and in-service training were significantly associated with healthcare utilization. Several factors influence health service utilization among rural population. To improve utilization, interventions should incorporate multifaceted factors to tackle socioeconomic barriers, financial difficulties, geographic constraints and digital health technologies, enhancing residents' competency through education and financial empowerment.

KEYWORDS: Health service utilization, rural Ghana, Andersen model, health insurance, provider factors, universal health coverage.

INTRODUCTION

Utilising healthcare services poses a significant challenge in rural Ghana, with many individuals facing difficulties in obtaining the necessary health services (Tuoyire et al., 2024). Despite substantial investments in Ghana's healthcare system, such as the introduction of the National Health Insurance Scheme (NHIS), establishment of health institutions, training of different cadre of healthcare staff as well as implementation of community-based health planning and services (CHIPs) compound through the primary healthcare programme, rural communities still encounter significant obstacles in utilising health services (Ketor et al., 2024). Studies indicate that healthcare utilization in Ghana averages merely 1.1 outpatient visits per person annually, which is significantly below the recommended standards (Amoah-Nuamah et al., 2023; Tuoyire et al., 2024). The low utilization rate indicates that numerous individuals in need of healthcare are not receiving it, especially in rural areas.

Ghana's healthcare system has seen significant advancements in recent decades; however, notable deficiencies persist, particularly in rural areas (Amoah-Nuamah et al., 2023). There are factors hinder its utilisation. These factors are multifaceted and multidimensional and it is crucial to comprehend the factors that drive individuals to pursue healthcare to enhance health outcomes to meet the objectives of universal health coverage. Research has identified three primary categories of factors influencing healthcare

utilization: individual and household characteristics, health system factors, and community-level influences (Ketor et al., 2024). Factors such as age, education level, income, and marital status significantly influence healthcare-seeking behaviour in Ghana (Agyemang-Duah et al., 2020).

Health system factors that influence healthcare utilization include proximity to healthcare facilities, treatment costs, quality of care delivered, and the manner in which healthcare workers interact with patients (Kodom & Netangaheni, 2024). Geographic barriers are significant, as a study Amoah-Nuamah et al. (2023) indicates that 50.5% of rural communities struggle to access health facilities within the recommended distance. Subpar road conditions, restricted transportation choices, and extended travel durations present further challenges for individuals seeking medical care (Korah et al., 2023). Financial barriers continue to be a significant issue in healthcare utilisation, even with the implementation of the NHIS (Domapielle et al., 2023; Nsiah-Boateng et al., 2019). The insurance scheme has enhanced access for numerous Ghanaians; however, coverage is still inconsistent and poorly funded, as rural and low-income households are less likely to be insured than their urban and wealthier counterparts (Nsiah-Boateng et al., 2019). Insured patients frequently encounter unofficial payments and indirect costs, including transportation and lost wages, which may deter them from pursuing the necessary care (Domapielle et al., 2023).

Factors related to healthcare providers significantly impact individuals' utilization of health services. Studies have indicated that the attitudes, knowledge, and experience of healthcare workers influence patients' readiness to seek care (Agyemang-Duah et al., 2020; Escribano-Ferrer et al., 2016). Negative attitudes exhibited by healthcare providers may deter patients from attending follow-up appointments or seeking assistance for future health problems. Furthermore, insufficient staffing in rural health facilities results in a limited number of available providers being overburdened, potentially compromising the quality of care delivered. The quality and availability of health services significantly influence utilization patterns of health services. Escribano-Ferrer et al. (2016) highlighted ongoing issues with drug shortages, particularly in rural areas, where merely 30% of medications are sourced from the national procurement system. Equipment shortages and infrastructure issues restrict rural health facilities from delivering quality care, prompting some patients to seek treatment at more distant, better-equipped urban hospitals (Tuolong et al., 2024).

Analyzing healthcare utilization patterns is crucial for meeting Sustainable Development Goal 3, which aims to ensure healthy lives and promote well-being for everyone of all ages. The advancement of universal health coverage in Ghana relies on recognizing and addressing the obstacles that hinder individuals from obtaining necessary care (Korah et al., 2023). Investigating particular communities can yield important insights into local elements that affect healthcare-seeking behavior and guide focused interventions to enhance access (Korah et al., 2023; Tuolong et al., 2024). The focus of this study exemplifies rural communities that encounter significant obstacles in obtaining healthcare services. Identifying the factors that affect healthcare utilization can offer valuable insights relevant to comparable rural areas in Ghana and other developing countries.

This study determined the primary factors that predicted health service usage in the rural Ghana, specifically Sekyere Afram Plain, where the study was conducted faces a serious accessibility problem due to its location. It lacks motorable access due to hilly and water bodies surrounding the community, contributing greatly to the poor healthcare utilization, which has a negative influence on community member health status. This study aimed to offer evidence-based recommendations for enhancing healthcare access and utilization in rural Ghana by analyzing sociodemographic characteristics, health system factors, and healthcare provider-related factors. These findings would enhance the understanding of healthcare utilization in sub-Saharan Africa and guide policy decisions to ensure equitable healthcare access for all Ghanaians.

CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

This study was underpinned by the revised version of the Andersen Behavioral Model of Health Service Utilization as its theoretical framework. The Andersen model, which has been extensively validated in various populations, classifies healthcare utilization factors into three primary categories: predisposing, enabling, and need factors (Krzyż et al., 2023). This framework is especially applicable in rural areas, where various barriers concurrently affect healthcare-seeking behavior.

Predisposing factors are individual traits that exist before the onset of illness and affect the likelihood of utilizing healthcare services. Enabling factors refer to the resources and conditions that either promote or obstruct the utilization of healthcare services. These include individual resources, such as income and health insurance, and community resources, such as the availability and accessibility of facilities. Need factors include both perceived need, which refers to individual perceptions of health status, and evaluated need, which is based on a professionally assessed health status (Saah et al., 2021).

This study modifies the Andersen model to include factors specific to rural Ghana, acknowledging that healthcare utilization is affected by three areas: individual and household characteristics (socio-demographic factors and health beliefs), health system factors (distance, cost, quality of care, and waiting times), and healthcare provider factors (provider attitudes, knowledge, experience, and training). This adaptation corresponds with recent African studies highlighting provider-related factors in healthcare decisions (Agyemang-Duah and Rosenberg, 2023).

The conceptual framework recognizes that healthcare utilization arises from intricate interactions among individual, health system, and provider factors rather than from isolated determinants. Understanding these interactions is essential for creating

effective strategies to enhance healthcare access in rural areas and lays the theoretical groundwork for exploring the three research objectives of this study.

Figure 1: Conceptual framework for determinants of health service utilization in Rural Ghana

METHODS

Study Setting and Context

Sekyere Afram Plains district of Ashanti Region was the selected study site, which is mainly a district with most (83.1%) of residents in rural areas, providing an excellent context for examining rural healthcare utilization patterns (Egbenya et al., 2021). The district spans approximately 3,500.59 km² and had a population of 32,640, comprising 17,502 males and 15,138 females per the 2021 Population and Housing Census. The district is made up of one area council and ten unit committees (Ghana Statistical Service, 2021). The community encounters common rural issues, such as inadequate road infrastructure, restricted transportation alternatives, and access challenges during the rainy season.

The district is predominantly rural economy engaged in agriculture and its ancillary activities for livelihood. The main health facility in the district is the Sekyere Afram Plains District Hospital in Drobonso, however, there are smaller facilities like CHPS compounds and clinics, where most of these facilities are basic and located in remote places with poor access.

Study Design

A community-based analytical study was conducted to investigate the factors affecting healthcare utilization. This design is suitable for predict the factors influencing healthcare utilization at a specific point in time (Ketor et al., 2024). This design enables efficient data collection on various variables simultaneously and is appropriate for determining the relationships among sociodemographic characteristics, health system factors, and healthcare provider factors in relation to healthcare service utilization (Nuamah et al., 2019).

Sample Size and sampling method

The target population included adult (>19) resident in Sekyere Afram Plains District who had lived there for a minimum of six months before the study commenced. A sample size of 1,738 respondents was calculated from 15,144 reference adult population in Sekyere Afram Plains district using Krejcie and Morgan (1970) sample size table.

A multistage sampling technique, where a cluster sampling was used to put the district into clusters based on the unit committees and town council. Within each of the cluster, a systematic sampling method was used to select households in the community. A sampling frame was created by numbering all households (N=5,528) in Sekyere Afram Plains District according to the community's register. The sampling interval (k) was determined using the formula $k = N/n$, resulting in $k = 5,528/1,738 = 3.2$, which was rounded to every second household. A random starting point was established by choosing a number between 1 and 2, after which every second household was selected for the survey. In each chosen household, a single eligible adult was randomly selected through a lottery method if multiple eligible individuals were present.

Data Collection Procedure

Data were collected using a structured, pre-tested questionnaire administered through face-to-face interviews in the local language (Twi) or English, based on the participants' preferences. The questionnaire was created using the Andersen Behavioral Model of Health Service Utilization and included four primary sections: (1) sociodemographic characteristics (age, gender, educational level, marital status, occupation, income, and NHIS status), (2) health facility factors (distance to facility, cost of treatment, perceived quality of care, waiting time, and health insurance accreditation status), (3) healthcare provider factors (worker attitude, job knowledge, years of experience, and on-job training), and (4) healthcare utilization patterns (frequency of visits, types of services used, and reasons for seeking or not seeking care).

The questionnaire was first created in English, translated into Twi by bilingual professional, and subsequently back-translated into English to verify accuracy. A pre-test was conducted with 113 residents from a comparable community (excluded from the main study) to evaluate clarity, comprehensiveness, and cultural relevance. Changes were implemented following the pre-test results prior to the final data collection (Agyemang-Duah & Rosenberg, 2023).

In ensuring validity and reliability, content validity was established by conducting a thorough literature review and consulting public health experts and healthcare practitioners knowledgeable about rural Ghana. Two independent experts in health service research evaluated the questionnaire for relevance, clarity, and comprehensiveness. Pre-testing involved assessing face validity by gathering participant feedback on the clarity and comprehensibility of the questions. The evaluation of construct validity involved assessing whether the questionnaire items effectively measured the intended constructs outlined in Andersen's model. Inter-item correlations were analyzed to confirm that items within each construct were suitably related to each other.

Reliability was evaluated using Cronbach's alpha for scales consisting of multiple items. The healthcare utilization scale reached an α of 0.78, the health facility factors scale an α of 0.82, and the healthcare provider factors scale an α of 0.76, all surpassing the minimum threshold of 0.70 for acceptable internal consistency (Kumah et al., 2024). The test-retest reliability was evaluated by administering the questionnaire to a group of 40 participants again two weeks after the first data collection. The correlation coefficients varied between 0.73 and 0.89 for the different sections, demonstrating strong temporal stability.

Data collection was conducted over a six-months period, from March to September 2023, by a team of thirty trained research assistants fluent in English and Twi language. Household visits were conducted from 8:00 AM to 4:00 PM to ensure participant availability and accommodate community schedules. The interviews were conducted in private settings within the participants' homes, lasting approximately 15 to 34 minutes to maintain confidentiality. Research assistants outlined the study's purpose, secured informed consent, and distributed the questionnaires following standardized protocols. Daily debriefing sessions were conducted to address challenges, guarantee data quality, and uphold consistency among interviewers. Completed questionnaires were reviewed for completeness and accuracy prior to secure storage, and any missing information was addressed through follow-up visits within 48 hours.

Data Analysis

The data were input into Stata version 12.0 and analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics. The data cleaning process included the identification of outliers, handling of missing values, and resolution of inconsistencies. Descriptive statistics, such as frequencies, percentages, means, and standard deviations, were employed to characterize the study population and outline healthcare utilization patterns.

Chi-square tests was employed for inferential analysis to investigate the relationships between categorical variables and health care utilization. Binary logistic regression was used to determine the predictors of healthcare utilization, with the dependent variable coded as 1 for those who utilized healthcare services in the past 12 months and 0 for those who did not use them. The regression model incorporated sociodemographic factors, such as age, education, marital status, and income, as independent variables. The Hosmer-Lemeshow goodness-of-fit test was used to evaluate the model fit, where a p-value greater than 0.05 suggested a good fit.

Multiple linear regression was employed to analyze the impact of health facility factors on healthcare utilization, measured as a continuous variable indicating the frequency of visits. The model incorporated the distance to health facilities, treatment costs,

perceived care quality, patient waiting times, and health insurance accreditation status as independent variables. Diagnostic plots and tests were used to assess the model assumptions of normality, linearity, and homoscedasticity. Adjusted odds ratios (AOR) and 95% confidence intervals were computed to assess the strength of the associations. All analyses were conducted using a statistical significance threshold of $p < 0.05$ (Tuoyire et al., 2024).

Ethics

Approval for ethical considerations was obtained from the Institutional Review Board of the University of Health and Allied Sciences (Protocol Number: UHAS-REC A.1 [5] 21-22). Permissions were obtained from the Ashanti Regional Health Directorate, Sekyere Afram Plains district health directorate, and local leadership in communities.

All participants provided either written or oral informed consent after being thoroughly educated about the study's purpose, procedures, risks, benefits, and their rights as research participants. Participants were made aware that they could withdraw from the study at any time without facing any repercussions. Confidentiality, anonymity and privacy were upheld through the use of secured places, unique identification numbers and restricted access to information.

RESULTS

Socio-demographic Characteristics of Respondents

The descriptive statistics render information on the demographic and professional profiles of the participants surveyed (N = 1,738). The age range portrays that most (65.7%) are in the 36-35 years range, trailed by 21.6% in the 20-25 years range, and a negligible percentage (0.9%) over 45 years. This reveals that young to middle-aged individuals dominate the district. By gender, women (53.8%) were slightly above men (46.2%), showing an equitable representation of the two genders. The level of education shows most respondents had basic (37.6%) and secondary (32.0%) educations, while 24.9% had no formal education. By occupation, farming (60.4%) constitute a higher percentage compared to those working for others such government and private entity as employees (39.6%). Larger portion of the residents had valid health insurance (61.8%), and married (62.7%) as compared to those uninsured (38.2%) and unmarried (37.3%). In relation to religious affiliation, majority (70.4%) were Christians and the rest were either Islam (22.2%) or others (7.4%). Resident' parity indicated that slightly above half (58.3%) had more than three children, followed by those with three children (28.1%) and least having one child (2.1%). The estimated household income per month indicated that almost two-third (60.3%) of the respondents had income between GH ₵1000 – 2,000, followed those above GH ₵2,000 (24.6%) and few below GH ₵ 1,000 (15.1%). The standard deviations and means also bear witness to a very homogeneous sample in terms of age, sex, education, occupation, insurance status, and income level.

Table 1: Socio-demographic Characteristics of Participants (N=1,738)

Variables	Frequency	Percentage	Mean	Std. Deviation	Variance
Age Category			1.9201	.60375	.365
20-25 Years	375	21.6			
26-35 Years	1142	65.7			
36-45 Years	205	11.8			
45+ Years	16	0.9			
Gender			1.5385	.49926	.249
Male	803	46.2			
Female	935	53.8			
Level of Education			2.1834	.87264	.762
No formal education	432	24.9			
Basic	653	37.6			
Secondary education	556	32.0			
Tertiary	97	5.6			
Occupation			1.3964	.48989	.240
Farming	1050	60.4			
Employee	688	39.6			
Caregiver NHIS status			2.6453	0.7430	.563
Insured	1074	61.8			
Uninsured	664	38.2			
Marital status			1.9542	0.5231	.421
Married	1090	62.7			
Unmarried	648	37.3			
Religious affiliation			4.0451	0.695	.443

Christianity	1224	70.4			
Islam	385	22.2			
Others	129	7.4			
Parity			3.320	0.242	.305
1	36	2.1			
2	200	11.5			
3	489	28.1			
3+	1013	58.3			
Estimated household income per month			3.0266	.77949	.608
< GH ¢ 1,000	262	15.1			
GH ¢ 1000 – 2,000	1048	60.3			
> GH ¢ 2,000	428	24.6			

Socio-Demographic Factors Influencing Utilization of Health Service

The binary logistic regression model was statistically significant, $\chi^2 (66) = 98.102.25, p = 0.001$. The Nagelkerke R^2 of the model explained 58.2% of the variance in utilization of health service and it accurately classifies 82.9% of the services. Hosmer and Lemeshow test indicated a model of good fit to the data at [$\chi^2 (7) = 12.625, p = 1.321$], predicting the probability of membership of health service utilization.

The outcome of the binary logistic regression model showed that almost all the socio-demographic factors of residents were significant predictors of health service utilization and statistically significant, except gender and occupational status. Thus, the results showed that age – $\chi^2 = 6.416, p = 0.001$; educational level – $\chi^2 = 2.145, p = 0.003$; marital status – $\chi^2 = 5.416, p = 0.000$; and income per month – $\chi^2 = 8.654, p = 0.023$ predicted utilization of health service.

Table 3 also illustrated that adults (36 – 60 years) were 1.86 times more likely not to utilize healthcare service as compared to the younger adults [20 – 35 years], (C.I. = 0.401 – 6.313). However, the aged (>60+ years) were 2.15 times more likely to utilize health services than the younger adults (C.I. = 0.519 – 17.291). This means that utilization of health service is likely to be higher among the aged than young adults, whereas the adults were not likely to use health service.

Table 2: Binary logistic regression of socio-demographic factors on service utilization

Factors	Categories	B	S.E.	Wald	Sig	OR	95% C. I
Constant		-1.93	0.66	16.02	0.003	1.42	
Age	Adults	-0.87	0.45	6.32	0.002	1.86	0.401 – 6.313
	Aged	1.01	0.97	7.37	0.001	2.15	0.519 – 17.291
Education	Basic	0.87	0.28	4.31	0.005	1.23	0.037 – 9.018
	Secondary	0.22	0.49	9.90	0.023	1.82	1.366 – 11.524
	Tertiary	0.66	0.82	11.23	0.000	1.99	1.720 – 25.722
Marital status	Unmarried	-0.54	0.25	5.29	0.021	0.09	0.629 – 18.251
Income per month	500 – 1,000	0.82	0.71	13.33	0.023	1.04	0.712 – 18.218
	1,000 – 2,000	1.23	0.91	13.90	0.001	1.23	0.614 – 19.018
	>2,000	1.39	0.89	9.27	0.003	3.21	0.771 – 22.910
Gender	Male	-0.63	0.52	8.99	0.045	2.71	0.231 – 6.218
Occupation	Unemployed	-1.18	0.86	6.32	0.121	3.63	1.028 – 13.317
	Student	-0.61	0.62	4.44	0.510	3.12	0.286 – 9.092

With regards to participants’ educational level, basic education (C.I. = 0.037 – 9.018), secondary education (C.I. = 1.366 – 11.524) and tertiary education (C.I. = 1.720 – 25.722) holders were 1.23 times, 1.82 times, and 1.99 times more likely to utilize health services as compared to those with no formal education. This means that utilization of health service increases with higher education.

Predictive Factors for Health Service Utilization in Rural Ghana: A Community-Based Analytical Study

The study revealed that the unmarried were 0.09 times less likely not to utilize health service than the married ones (C.I. = 0.629 – 18.251). Thus, marriage has an influence on health service utilization. Participants with income between GH ₵ 500 – 1,000 were 1.04 times more likely to utilize health service than those below GH ₵ 500 (C.I. = 0.712 – 18.218). Also, participants with income between GH ₵ 1,00 – 2,000 (C.I. = 0.614 – 19.108) and above GH ₵ 2,000 (C.I. = 0.771 – 22.910) were 1.23 times and 3.21 times more likely to utilize health services than participants with lower income. Thus, utilization of health services increases with high income.

Perceived Health Provider Factors Associated with Utilization of Health Service

The model revealed that distance to health facility factors; specifically cost of treatment, perceived quality of care and patient waiting time were significant predictors of utilization of health services [$F(5.6, 335) = 15.201$ and $p = 0.002$]. The coefficient of determination (R^2 adj = 0.695) indicated that distance to health facility, cost of treatment, perceived quality of care and patient waiting time explained 69.5% variability of utilization of health services.

The model in Table 3 illustrates that distance to health facility, cost of treatment, perceived quality of care and patient waiting time individually significantly predicted the utilization of health services at the 5% level of significance representing: $t = 7.506, p = 0.000$; $t = 4.587, p = 0.001$; $t = -5.562, p = 0.004$ and $t = 5.679, p = 0.021$, respectively.

Table 3: Regression of Health Facility Factors Influencing Utilization of Health Services

Model	B	Std. Error	Beta	t	Sig.	Tolerance	VIF
Constant	89.456	4.036		20.451	0.000		
Health insurance accreditation status	5.201	1.505	0.408	3.455	0.001	0.880	1.137
Distance to health facility	11.073	2.248	0.631	4.927	0.000	0.581	1.722
Perceived quality of care	-4.085	1.756	-0.369	-2.326	0.022	0.526	1.900
Cost of treatment	13.830	2.432	0.721	4.772	0.031	0.772	1.882
Waiting Time	5.763	1.821	0.405	3.082	0.021	0.448	1.173

The standardised beta coefficients indicated that cost of treatment had the highest influence on utilization of health services since it contributed 72.1% in variability in health service utilization. This means that a change will cost of treatment is likely to result in a huge improvement in utilization of health services. However, there is 27.9% that could not be explained in health service utilization by cost of treatment. Also, second highest variable that contributed to change in utilization of health services was distance to health facility. The distance to health facility contributed 63.1% of variability in utilization of health services. Therefore, holding all things constant, a change in distance to health facility will lead to an increase in utilization of health services.

The standardised beta coefficients, further indicated that health insurance accreditation status was able to explain 40.8% variability in utilization of health services. Thus, any change in the health insurance accreditation status of the facility will cause 40.8% improvement in utilization of health services. Also, patient waiting time contributed to 40.5% of variability in utilization of health services. Thus, all thing being equal, a change in patient waiting time will lead to an increase in utilization of health services. Finally, perceived quality of treatment accounted for only 36.9% of variability in utilization of health services. It implied that a change in perceived quality of care, holding all other factors constant, will lead to a decrease in utilization of health services. Thus, perceived quality of care did not have a positive influence on utilization of health services. Interestingly, perceived quality of care could not explain 63.1% variability in utilization of health services.

Health Provider Factors Associated with Utilization of Health Service

The results in Table 5 illustrated an association between health provider factors and utilization of health services. The results showed that all the health provider factors were statistically significant at $p > 0.05$. This implied that health provider factors (workers attitude, job knowledge, years of work experience and on-job training) were significantly associated with utilization of health services.

Specifically, attitude of workers was significantly associated with utilization of health services, with p -value=0.000 and AOR= 0.734. Also, job knowledge was significant associated with utilization of health services at p -value = 0.022 and AOR = 3.866. In addition, years of work experience was statistically associated with utilization of health services at p -vale = 0.021 and AOR = 3.054. Finally, on-job training was also significantly associated with utilization of health services at p -value = 0.004 and AOR = 2.036.

Table 4: Association Between Health Provider Factors and Health Service Utilization

Health provider factors	Categories	Utilization health services		Total	AOR (95% C.I.)	p-value
		Yes f (%)	No f (%)			
Attitude of workers					0.734(0.44-1.44)	0.000
	Good	106 (6.1)	139 (8.0)	245 (14.1)		
	Poor	820 (47.2)	673 (38.7)	1493 (85.9)		
Job knowledge					3.866(1.8-7.9)	0.022
	Adequate	42 (2.3)	387 (22.3)	429 (24.7)		
	Poor	885 (50.9)	424 (24.4)	1309 (75.3)		
Years of work experience					3.054(1.6-5.57)	0.021
	Long years/experienced	318 (18.3)	388 (22.3)	706 (40.6)		
	Few years/inexperienced	608 (35.0)	424 (24.4)	1032 (59.4)		
On-job training					2.036(1.7-5.32)	0.004
	Adequately trained	104 (6.1)	370 (21.3)	474 (27.3)		
	Poorly trained	822 (47.2)	442 (25.4)	1264 (72.7)		

*N = 1738

DISCUSSION

This study identified determinants of health service utilization in rural Ghana, revealing that sociodemographic characteristics, health facility factors, and provider-related attributes collectively shape healthcare-seeking behaviour. The results question traditional beliefs regarding the effectiveness of health insurance in rural areas and emphasize the ongoing impact of structural obstacles on access to health care.

The correlation between education and healthcare usage is consistent with the evidence from sub-Saharan Africa, highlighting the urgent need for educational interventions (Kumah et al., 2024). A national analysis of Ghana's 2017 Living Standards Survey identified education as a key factor influencing health service utilization, with the strongest correlation found among individuals with tertiary education (Tuoyire et al., 2024). The educational gradient, which shows a 1.99 times higher utilization of healthcare for those with tertiary education compared to those with no education, goes beyond health literacy. These include factors such as cultural capital, social networks, and the skills needed to navigate complex healthcare systems. Comparable trends have been observed in additional rural Ghanaian research (Ketor et al., 2024), indicating that educational attainment reliably influences healthcare-seeking behaviours and preferences for service quality.

The income-utilization gradient shows that participants earning over GH¢2,000 were 3.21 times more likely to use the services. This suggests that Ghana's poverty reduction strategies must include health service accessibility measures beyond insurance coverage (Adawudu et al., 2024). Recent evidence from the NHIS evaluation by Sarkodie (2021) indicates that enrollment boosts healthcare utilization by 26%, yet only decreases out-of-pocket payments by 4%, highlighting ongoing financial barriers. The income effect observed here surpasses those documented in other sub-Saharan African regions, where such effects usually fall between 1.5 and 2.5 times, indicating a greater degree of economic stratification in rural Ghana's healthcare access (Sarkodie, 2021).

The surprising discovery that unmarried individuals are less inclined to use health services utilization contradicts Western literature while aligning with African social structures, where married individuals benefit from broader support networks (Domapielle et al., 2023). Recent qualitative evidence from rural northern Ghana indicates that family proximity and social support play significant roles in healthcare-seeking behaviour (Okyere et al., 2021). Thus, married individuals benefit from improved access to transportation assistance and financial-pooling mechanisms. In rural Ghana, marriage offers emotional support and practical help, including assistance with healthcare navigation, childcare during illness, and financial pooling for medical expenses, to older adults.

Additionally, utilization patterns based on age indicate that adults aged 36-60 are less inclined to use services, whereas individuals over 60 years are more likely to seek care. This trend highlights the differing life priorities and perceptions of health needs among various age groups. A recent study by Babagoli et al. (2024), conducted in four rural communities in northern Ghana,

revealed comparable age-related trends, indicating that middle-aged adults exhibited a higher prevalence of hypertension (16.4% among those aged 51-70 compared to 7.6% among those aged 35-50). However, in this study, this demographic group demonstrated lower healthcare utilization, which was attributed to economic responsibilities. The U-shaped pattern indicates that middle-aged adults encounter conflicting work and family obligations, which may hinder their pursuit of healthcare, even when their health needs are significant.

The significant influence of cost (72.1% variance) and distance (63.1% variance) factors undermines Ghana's belief that health insurance alone guarantees equitable access to healthcare. Although NHIS coverage has reached 55% nationally, rural residents continue to encounter significant financial obstacles, indicating that having insurance does not ensure its use (Ghana Health Service, 2024). Korah et al. (2023) found that in the Upper West region of rural Ghana, only 61% of the population has access to primary healthcare facilities that meet the recommended standards, and the distance barriers differ notably depending on the mode of transportation. The NHIS addresses direct service costs; however, it does not cover transportation, accommodation for referrals, lost wages, or informal payments that continue to exist in rural facilities.

Geographic accessibility analyses utilizing GIS technology indicate that 50.5% of rural communities are unable to reach health facilities within the distance thresholds recommended by the WHO, with numerous residents traveling more than 5 km for basic care (Amoah Nuamah et al., 2023). A recent spatial analysis of Offinso North District revealed significant disparities in healthcare accessibility across sub-districts, with certain areas exhibiting doctor-patient ratios as low as 0.015:1,000, in stark contrast to the WHO's recommended ratio of 1:1,000 (Nsiah et al., 2024). The findings of this study reveal distance effects that underscore systematic inequities in facility placement, favoring administrative convenience over the access patterns of the population.

The negative link between perceived quality of care and its utilization is a significant finding that requires immediate attention. Current evidence indicates that only 30% of drugs provided in rural health facilities originate from national procurement systems, while ongoing stock-outs and quality concerns continue to erode patient confidence (Escribano-Ferrer et al., 2016). Ketor et al. (2024) conducted a study in rural districts and identified affordability (59.9% of respondents), drug availability, and service quality as the key factors affecting healthcare-seeking behaviour. Notably, poor service quality pushes patients towards traditional healers and pharmacies. In contrast to urban areas, where enhancements in quality usually lead to higher usage, rural quality improvement initiatives face distinct obstacles, such as fundamental infrastructure, equipment reliability, and consistency of services.

The relationship between provider attitude (AOR=0.734), job knowledge (AOR=3.866), and experience (AOR=3.054) in relation to health service utilization highlights significant human resource deficiencies that necessitate comprehensive workforce development strategies. Okyere et al. (2021) studied 68 healthcare workers in Ghana's Upper East Region and found that insufficient supervision, isolation, and limited career advancement opportunities notably affect rural healthcare workers' motivation and performance. The negative relationship between worker attitude and utilization contrasts with the conventional healthcare quality literature. This indicates that in situations where healthcare alternatives are available, negative provider attitudes can push patients away from formal services and towards traditional healers or pharmacy-based care.

Additionally, the results indicating that 85.9% of workers exhibited poor attitudes and 75.3% displayed insufficient knowledge require urgent focus on enhancing provider competency (Adongo et al., 2024). Asamani et al. (2018) conducted a workforce forecasting study that revealed Ghana meets only 68% of its health workforce needs, highlighting significant shortages, especially in specialists and experienced practitioners. The significant knowledge gaps among providers highlight systematic failures in developing Ghana's rural health workforce. Only 32% of the national health workforce is located in predominantly rural regions, which have the highest health needs.

Furthermore, the cross-sectional study by Amalba et al. (2018) on medical doctors in Ghana's Northern Region indicates that income disparity, limited career advancement opportunities, insufficient housing, and heavy workloads are key factors that deter rural practice. In contrast to urban facilities that regularly implement continuous medical education programs, rural facilities frequently lack organized systems for maintaining competency. The lack of knowledge significantly influences the management of common conditions and the decision-making process for referrals, which, in turn, affects patient trust in formal healthcare services.

The notable link between on-the-job training and utilization (AOR=2.036) suggests that ongoing professional development plays a crucial role in enhancing service quality and patient satisfaction. Recent evaluations of continuing professional development strategies for more than 10,000 health workers in Ghana have shown that combining e-learning with in-person training can effectively enhance the capacity of healthcare workers (Salehi et al., 2023). The discovery that 72.7% of providers lacked adequate training indicates significant deficiencies in continuing education systems, especially in rural regions, where training opportunities are scarce and supervision is inconsistent.

The findings indicate that Ghana's rural pipeline programs, despite increasing participation, have not effectively tackled issues related to competency and attitude. Alhassan et al. (2017) conducted an analysis comparing health tutors in rural and urban training institutions, highlighting significant disparities in educational resources and support systems. The findings indicate that rural institutions are deficient in supervision and professional development opportunities. The existing medical education framework results in healthcare providers who are ill-equipped for rural settings, necessitating a reformation of training programs to focus on cultural competency and skills tailored to rural environments. International support, such as the recent £15 million Global Health

Workforce Programme aimed at Ghana, Kenya, and Nigeria, presents opportunities for extensive workforce development initiatives (UK DHSC, 2023).

Interventions must prioritize cost-sharing mechanisms that tackle transportation and indirect costs, rather than solely focusing on service fees. Mobile health (mHealth) technologies present cost-effective solutions for follow-up care and health education in Ghana, where mobile penetration stands at 95% (Peprah et al., 2020). However, addressing literacy barriers is essential. Provider survey indicated a lack of awareness regarding mHealth applications, highlighting significant gaps in the implementation of technology versus its actual use. Medium-term strategies necessitate thorough development programs for providers that focus on enhancing both technical expertise and interpersonal abilities. Improved supervision systems, ongoing education, and performance-based incentives may enhance provider attitudes and knowledge at the same time. Long-term reforms must incorporate healthcare accessibility within Ghana's decentralization framework, enabling districts to have the autonomy to create tailored interventions that address local barriers. The One-District-One-Ambulance initiative necessitates supporting policies that focus on improving road infrastructure and communication systems.

LIMITATIONS

The cross-sectional design limits causal inference; however, the strength of the associations indicates significant relationships. Self-reported healthcare usage can lead to recall bias, particularly concerning minor illnesses. The focus on a single community restricts the ability to generalize the findings, although the traits of Sekyere Afram Plains reflect those of numerous rural communities in Ghana. Responses regarding provider attitudes may have been influenced by social desirability bias; however, anonymous data collection likely reduced this impact.

Although the Andersen model is thorough, it might overlook certain Africa-specific elements, such as traditional healing practices or the influence of extended family in decision-making processes. Future research should utilize mixed-methods approaches and longitudinal designs to determine causality and investigate the unmeasured cultural factors.

CONCLUSION

The use of healthcare services in rural Ghana is influenced by a variety of factors, including personal attributes, shortcomings within the health system, and deficiencies in provider skills, which go beyond financial obstacles. The ongoing impact of education, income, and marital status shows that achieving healthcare equity necessitates broader social progress beyond mere reforms in the health sector. The influence of cost and distance factors, even with insurance coverage, highlights essential flaws in health system design that favor urban accessibility over rural. The negative relationship between perceived quality and utilization suggests that rural health services might be compromising their goals because of inadequate service delivery.

To achieve universal health coverage in rural Ghana, it is essential to move away from the belief that insurance coverage guarantees access to healthcare. Interventions should address economic barriers through comprehensive cost-sharing, enhance service quality by developing provider competencies, and mitigate geographic barriers using technology and transportation solutions. The 59.5% unexplained variance in this study's models indicates considerable potential for innovative interventions that tackle unmeasured factors, such as cultural preferences, social networks, and community-specific barriers. Achieving success requires collaborative efforts among the education, transport, and health sectors, instead of focusing solely on improvements within the health system. Ghana can only achieve equitable healthcare access for its rural populations and make progress toward Sustainable Development Goal 3 through comprehensive approaches.

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